

ATTITUDINAL CHANGES OF WOMEN VOLUNTEERS THROUGH INNOVATIVE NSS PROGRAMMES

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There is no force more powerful than women determined to rise."

Mahatma Gandhi Called women as the noble sex.

"There is no chance of the welfare of the World unless the condition of the Women improved.

It is not possible for a bird to fly on one wind."

Swami Vivekananda

NSS (National Service Scheme)

The National Service Scheme is popularly known as NSS, is a central sector scheme of Government of India, Ministry of Youth Affairs & Sports. Girls empowerment is a process of learning through which girls identify their own Potentiality. If a girl has the ability to change a home into sweet home then she has all the capacities to change a society into healthy & happy society at the same time a Developing Nation.

Empowerment of the girl in the right direction is the call of the hour today. In the age of Globalization adolescent girls often struggle with certain specific challenges such as gender discrimination eve teasing, alcoholism, during abuse, trafficking, early marriage, adolescent pregnancy, rape, cybercrimes, peer pressure, bulging, assault, substance use, mental depression etc. Are quite rampant now a day in our society. Considering the multifarious and deep rooted problems faced but young girls in India there is a need to consider this section a high risk and highly vulnerable and requires urgent attention and action.

To make the adolescent girls more competent to face the challenges they need to be motivated in a positive way to face the changing world. In their student life they should be engaged growing their personality, build confidence and build them into a strong minded, disciplined and patriotic citizen of the country, so that they can be saved from the trapped, torture demotivation, depression and suppression.

2. Importance of NSS for girls

NSS is a wonderful platform for the young girls to awake them. It guides of their own mind and make them responsible citizen of the country. NSS trains and grooms the young minds as strong-minded person, a youth leader, and a community organizer in walks of life. Youth power is the biggest power of the country, if they are well trained , rightly motivated and build up strongly in their foundation period of life they can shape their life dutifully and shape the future of the Nation as a whole.

3. The objectives of NSS are to:-

1. Understand themselves and their potential
2. Build character, discipline & Nationalism
3. Develop a sense of social & civic responsibility
4. Understand themselves in relation to their community
5. Identify the needs and the problems of the community and involve them in problem solving.
6. Gain skills in mobilizing community participation.
7. Acquire leadership qualities and democratic attitudes.
8. Develop capacity to meet emergencies and natural disaster.
9. Practices National Instigation and Social harmony.

The objective, Motto & Activities motivated the young girl to come forward to join NSS. The involvement in different activities and learning many lessons through Regular & Special camping programme. Camps like NI Camp, SI Camp help them to exchange and grow the cultural habits, ideas and differences, at one place this is also a great platform for showcase their talent, abilities & capacities.

The camp activates encourage social interaction, improve concentration and learning, increase personal confidence and self awareness. The recreation activities make them healthy and happy as a whole which is the need of the time now.

To encourage the volunteers, Govt. also gives difference award and weightages to girl's volunteers. Women always have constructive role in the society, yet they face severe
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oppressions and injustices which are sourcing to the modern mankind the social costume are made in the favour of men and against women. Women should have greater role in socio cultural, politico-economical development of a nation. The empowered women can lead the nation various fields in NSS girls get inspired, encouraged to think and work for themselves first then for the community. They learn to expand their limits. They learn to give a helping hand to all. They motivated to work for the society.

Compare to the past data now a day more and more girls showing their interest in NSS. They proved that in no way they are inferior to men. The day when every girls will start working for themselves standing in equal level with boys that is the day we can proudly say that every one is equal and we can see our country as developed. The strong and empower girls are necessary for strong India. Our NSS can also contribute in the novel aim by calling more girl volunteers.

Now day's parents also show interest to enroll their girls into NSS and self-defense to make their girls more competent and independent. In the earlier times, the parent interest was very low because of social structure and fear. The Programme Officers role also very crucial as they motivate young minds to enroll into NSS by explaining the positive outcomes. Girls' volunteers are more sincere, disciplines and highly motivated when they got an opportunity and platform like NSS. "A comparative study of empowerment of NSS and non NSS Girl volunteers" conducted by Biswamitra Purohit and Dr. Iswar Patel conducted that NSS is a platform, which develop and empower adolescent girl volunteers. In the present scenario parents, teachers and the educational institutions are very aware of different problems in competitive future life. It will be very helpful if we will encourage young girls to join NSS. The study founds a significant difference in NSS girls empowerment (autonomy and self-reliance) compare to non NSS girls volunteers compare to Non NSS girls. "The most beautiful thing a girl can wear is confidence "and confidence is possible through a platform like NSS. Strong women can build a strong Nation.

Self-defense training programme for girls students or girls volunteers is one of the major innovative programme needful for their attitudinal changes. This self-defense training programme for college girls implemented by Odisha Government is a Flagship programme under the State Youth policy announced in the year 2013 under this programme a huge number of girls students and volunteers were imparted self-defense training and skills from the college level to make them able to defend against physical assault. This programme not only empowered the girl volunteers rather boost their moral high, it made them feeling self-
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confident, fearless and the strength to feel self-sufficient to go and work at any place, any surrounding any time. This has added an over pleasing impact on the socio-economic growth of the society and the country. As a result, we find the girls or women contribution in defense sector, digital sector, corporate sector, social sector and so many. Their learned dedication perseverance physical emotional and situational strength bring attitudinal changes and they behave accordingly. An instance fastness comes in them.

Gender sensitization is another innovative programme especially planned for girls. Stress is given to the ethics and sense of equality as provided by the constitution of India. It appeals to a great concern of raising awareness and sensitization in gender equality. This programme helps the girls volunteers in self-experiencing their personal attitudes whatever may be in item. It also makes them to make a comparative study of their belief with reality from the fanciful ideas of the world. The reality is par with the privileges referred in the constitution and the pragmatic approaches life in society. In a country like India as highly rural based this gender sensitization informative programme helps the girls and the society to be at par with male and the girls are able to do all kinds of activities and services.

Youth leadership programme is a youth encouraging innovative programme where the girl volunteers are giving ample opportunities in building the sense of leadership qualities in them.

So many Youth Leadership programmes like:- District level youth leadership camp, organization of various state level camps, trainings, symposiums build the spirit of coming forwarded to lead a group or team i.e. building leadership among the youths are organized for them . The youth leadership innovative programme have facilities that to be one the girls pro-human centered and to make design their thought for the resolution of social complexities, challenges, need to make themselves self earned and honoured.

The girl's volunteers are evoked with such innovative youth leadership programmes, that has helped themselves both in building leadership qualities and identifies with professional social status. By this, they become truthful honest, disciplined, be integrated with the various situational and worldly changes. This kind attitudinal differences we see after the youth leadership programme among the girl volunteers.

Integrated youth development and internship programme is a marvelous and attractive innovative programme for the girl volunteers. The involvement and participations of the girl volunteers is an opportunity to know and work in the field at public sector and to obtain knowledge in relation to the functioning at local and state government operations. They have a very good command of the English and other languages, they are made skilled as per their

capabilities and allowed serve as per the job allotted and described for. The girl volunteers work being an internship with more promisingly to deliver the quality work or service at the best. The girl volunteers find an exposure to get equipped through this innovative internship programme as a trainee to work and get set in the various jobs and services as facilitated by different Governmental, Corporate, Banking, Private Organization sections. By participating in these types of programmes they get an across to be accelerated as a preparatory workforce to get set in society and life. Such programmes have provided common platforms to the girl volunteer for meaningful interactions, empirical analysis at data, reports and beefing of ideas, formulation of policies, mitigation of gender issues and gaps ensuring promptness in society and total collaboration of managing things skillfully. Directly and indirectly, it has helped the girl's volunteers to be self-empowered and self-independent.

Adventure programmes are also the innovative programmes planned for the girl's volunteers.

Such programmes are exclusively designed for the adolescent girls or the girl being a part of institutional believing or upholding. We find a varieties at adventure programmes including Tree Climbing, Rock Climbing, Sea Kayaking, Mountaineering, Back Packing, Canyoneering Mountain Biking, Swimming, Diving etc. Looking at the camp designing, feasibilities the choices are made the adventure programme to be adopted for girl volunteers. This kind of innovative programmes largely focus as a supporting positive physical, social and emotional growth of girl. Before designing the programme their safety, security features are examined, they are made free from the stereotyped mindsets and connection. It helps them to come out from heir negative behaviour and develops a synthesis of the common multiple behavioural approaches, a learning adjustment to the various aspects of life and society. In relation to this programmes for girls, so many camps are conducted, organized, worked as platforms where they participated, exercise and develop such habits, instincts behaviour in them that, it has seen that at the end of the camp get emotional but confident. They seem to find a spirit of doing anything that they were fearful of. The buildings of self-confidence to rock the word seems to be the findings.

It is seen that the girls are more witty. Various results of some of the important entrance tests, examinations are published with a rating that the girls have topped. So in the institutional level various innovative programmes are designed or adopted to boost the girls moral, wit and activities. Such educative themes or contents are adopted that the girls volunteers can receive, get equitable access to all the possibilities for future participation in society. Apart from conducting the wit accelerating programmes like- Debate, Essay Writing, Quiz, GK, Painting
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etc, some more other innovative programmes are regulated like Crafting, Painting, Health Check up or nursing and themes related to the girls and gender centering issues like Poverty, Child Marriage, Gender-Based, Violence Domestic Slavery, Trafficking, No Tobacco or No Alcoholic issue etc. this very training, exposure of girls volunteers definitely build a sense of self-resilience both in the institution and society to think behind their boarder, belief, challenges and lives in the world and community. At time these girls volunteers must come out with the emerging resource of the family as “Family Guide” putting positive impact on the common men by inspiring them to be a good global citizen, that must change the society and the nation. This great attitudinal difference are experienced, gained and trained by the various innovative programmes especially meant for the girl’s volunteers to increase their talent and activities.

From the innovative programmes, it has been seen that, the girl volunteers are more interested as we find a rise in interesting in them. We find a bigger exercise, involvement in their learning and participation in multi socio culture aspects of society. Their participation in Integration camps, Adventure camps, Parade camps, Leadership camps, Cultural Fests etc, are some of the examples where the participation of girls volunteers have increased a lot. We see a sea of interest in them and this must help the society and nation to build at the best.

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